

Recipient Speaks

Mr. Anant Acharya
Software Engineer at SAP
Bengaluru

Anant Acharya**A Kidney Recipient & an Organ Donation Ambassador**

Life has a way of surprising us, often in ways we least expect. At 35, I faced one of the toughest challenges of my life a diagnosis of chronic kidney disease (CKD). For someone who lived a disciplined life - no smoking, no drinking - this diagnosis felt very unexpected. Faced with the choice between dialysis or a transplant, my wife's (Shradha Acharya) generous decision to donate her kidney gave me not only a second chance at life but also a renewed sense of purpose.

Last few years of my journey is defined by resilience, gratitude, and a desire to contribute to causes bigger than myself. This experience has shaped my perspective, allowing me to see both my personal and

professional roles through a broader lens.

Thanks to MOHAN Foundation for giving me an opportunity in engaging in philanthropic activities and providing me a platform to reach the larger audience. Becoming an organ donation ambassador has been a deeply fulfilling role for me. It allows me to connect with individuals and families who are considering organ donation, providing them with guidance and clarity. My own journey gives me the ability to address their fears, share real-life insights, and offer both practical and emotional support.

I enjoy running, hence post-transplant, I am participating in many Runs (5km or 10 km) to create awareness on the importance of physical activity for the transplant community. I always use these platforms to talk about organ donation and preventive measures for organ failure, which includes importance of monitoring blood pressure and Diabetes to the IT folks.

I have my own signature costume (Dhoti), which I wear and run for the awareness on the organ donation. I do participate in Regional and National transplant games and ensure to connect with our community to build my network and test my fitness journey.

I would thank my wife for giving me this second life and with which I can drive awareness on "Organ Donation " which is the need of the hour.

Corresponding Author: Dr. Sunil Shroff,
MOHAN Foundation, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India
Email: shroff@mohanfoundation.org

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